

Teaching Exploration on the Ideological and Political Education of Digital Image Processing under the Background of New Engineering

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Abstract: Ideological and political education is an important part of cultivating innovative talents with firm Ideology Political ideologies for national emerging industries under the background of new engineering. In the previous course teaching of "Digital Image Processing", the main focus was on explaining the knowledge points of the course without considering the exploration and integration of relevant ideological and political elements contained. According to the above issues, guided by the teaching goal of "trinity" of value shaping, ability cultivation, and knowledge teaching, a preliminary exploration is conducted on the ideological and political aspects of the Digital Image Processing. The paper takes the digital image processing course as an example to elaborate on the ideological and political teaching methods for professional courses. By exploring the ideological and political elements, reconstructing teaching design and changing teaching strategies, the ideological and political education of the course is integrated into the entire process of professional teaching, in order to achieve the education goal of "moistening things silently". Practice has shown that students' enthusiasm for learning this course has been significantly increased, and their satisfaction with the ideological and political content of the course is high, achieving the expected teaching effects.

Keywords: Curriculum Ideological and Political Education, Digital Image Processing, Establishing Virtue and Cultivating Talents.

1. Introduction

In December 2016, General Secretary xi jin-ping had an important speech at the National Conference on Ideological and Political Work in Higher Education Institutions, which clearly stated that "ideological and political work should be integrated into the entire process of education and teaching, achieving full and all-round education", as well as "all types of courses should go hand in hand with ideological and political theory courses, forming a synergistic effect" [1]. Since February 2017, the Ministry of Education actively promoted the construction of new engineering, and had formed the "Fudan Consensus" and "Tianda Action". The construction of new engineering compared with traditional engineering emphasized more on the practicality, intersectionality and comprehensiveness of disciplines in emerging industries, such as artificial intelligence, intelligent manufacturing, robots, cloud computing, etc [2]. In contrast to the distinctive characteristics of the new engineering major, digital image processing technology is not only an applied technology course in the field of artificial intelligence, but also fully possesses the characteristics of the new engineering major, which is bound to serve China's emerging industries[3]. In May 2020, the Ministry of Education issued the "Guidelines for the Ideological and Political Construction of Curriculum in Higher Education Institutions", which pointed out that "engineering courses should focus on strengthening students' engineering ethics education, cultivating students' spirit of striving for excellence as a great craftsman, and stimulating students' patriotism and mission responsibility for serving the country through science and technology" [4].

Integrating ideological and political education into all aspects of curriculum teaching and reform, to achieve the goal of cultivating morality and nurturing people by moistening things silently. Focusing on the curriculum goal of combining knowledge transmission and value guidance, we will construct a comprehensive curriculum education pattern [5], strengthen explicit ideological political education and refine implicit ideological political education. Contemporary youth should establish the lofty ideals and beliefs of communism, possess the ability to distinguish right from wrong, and develop a correct worldview, outlook on life and values. At present, some engineering students do not devote much attention to the importance of the study of ideological and political courses, and their learning enthusiasm is not very high. Therefore, engineering university education must build a comprehensive ideological and political education system, especially to fully leverage the ideological and political education role of various professional courses. While teaching professional knowledge, it is necessary to combine theory with application and integrate professional and ideological education to achieve the effect of moistening things silently in education.

The rapid development of artificial intelligence and other technologies have driven a new round of technological revolution and industrial transformation. In this context, the construction of new engineering courses has put forward new requirements for the core literacy and creative ability of innovative talents as an important development strategy for higher education in the new era. New engineering talents will must be the backbone of the future engineering technology field. Therefore, the question of which type talent to cultivate for the new engineering discipline has become the primary issue in higher education. Virtue is the foundation of being a person, and ideological and political education is the key link to implementing the fundamental task of cultivating morality and cultivating people in universities. With the arrival of the Personal media era, people can freely publish and spread their own opinions. The information is messy or mixed with all kinds of extreme and wrong information, which also brings higher difficulties and new challenges to the ideological and political education in universities. Therefore, integrating ideological and political elements into science and engineering courses can make ideological and political education more grounded and closely related to students' future career in the field of technology, more stimulating the interest of young students. Under the background of the construction of the new engineering discipline, the construction of a complete ideological and political curriculum system is an important measure to accelerate the cultivation of composite talents who love the party and patriotism and have solid basic knowledge with strong innovation ability, and they are willing to practice.

II. Problems of Ideological and Political Education in Digital Image Processing Course

In university engineering education, students spend most of their time studying engineering courses. Engineering courses have the characteristics of professionalism, practicality, innovation, and scientificity. Currently most of them focus on theoretical technology and lack the cultivation of scientific spirit and ethics [6]. There are several main problems in the ideological and political education of digital image processing courses.

1) Neglecting the important role of using professional courses to educate students on values, the awareness of using professional courses for ideological and political education is not strong and the ability to cultivate morality is insufficient.

2) The ideological and political education in the curriculum is not deep enough. There is a characteristic of emphasizing the impartation of knowledge and skills in teaching, ideological and political education is superficial and difficult to implement; teachers tend to

focus on professional knowledge teaching in specific education and teaching for tight academic schedules and heavy teaching tasks, However, education in terms of emotions, attitudes, and values often becomes mere formality, lacking a distinctive and dynamically adjusting auxiliary ideological and political curriculum system that integrates professional ethics, humanistic literacy, craftsmanship spirit, and model worker spirit education throughout the entire process of cultivation.

3) The construction of the content system for ideological and political education in the curriculum is incomplete. Currently ideological and political education in courses has become the main theme of teaching reform in universities, but the construction plan and standards of ideological and political education of digital image processing courses are still in the exploratory stage. Teachers can consciously integrate ideological and political elements into course teaching, but there is no relatively mature curriculum system that combining ideological and political education with professional courses.

Therefore, integrating ideological and political elements into science and engineering courses can make ideological and political education more vivid, grounded, and closely related to students' future career in the field of technology, thus more appealing to young students. Under the background of the construction of the new engineering, a complete ideological and political curriculum system is an important measure to accelerate the cultivation of composite talents who love the party and patriotism, have solid basic knowledge and strong innovation ability, and are willing to practice.

III. Strategies for Integrating Ideological and Political Education into Professional Course Teaching

Professional course teachers are important forces in carrying out ideological and political education for students in universities. Introducing ideological and political education into professional course teaching is currently the primary goal of professional course teaching reform, and is also an important supplement to ideological and political education in universities, to enable students to master knowledge to the maximum extent in the classroom, stimulating their interest in learning, providing ideological and political education to students silently, and cultivating innovative new engineering talents for society.

3.1 Professional teachers have a correct understanding of curriculum ideology and politics

The main body of ideological and political education in curriculum is not only teachers, but also managers and student workers. It should focus on curriculum education, professional education, and subject education. To deeply analyze the ideological and political elements that can be explored in the course knowledge points, establish teaching objectives for emotional attitudes and values, and cultivate students' sense of professional identity and recognition of excellent Chinese traditional culture. Integrating ideological and political education into professional course teaching can promote professional course teachers to devote importance to the role of words and deeds. Integrating ideological and political elements with professional knowledge and skills in teaching design can subtly influence the cultivation of students' professional literacy and ideological and moral cultivation. Teachers integrate the ideological and political elements into professional courses silently, making students think and feel about what they have learned.

3.2 Enhancing the ability of ideological and political for professional teachers

Curriculum ideological and political education belongs to implicit ideological and political education, so educational activities should be carried out for students at appropriate educational contexts to achieve the goal of influence people [7]. Curriculum ideological and political education is not simply adding some craftsmanship spirit, chinese excellent traditional culture and advanced deeds to the curriculum, but it requires overall design at the beginning, organically integrating ideological and political elements into professional talent training goals, such as traditional art, Chinese wisdom, revolutionary traditions, etc [8], Teachers should grasp the core elements of ideological and political construction in the curriculum, and further strengthen their conscious awareness of cultivating morality and cultivating people [9].

IV. Analysis of Ideological and Political Elements in Curriculum

4.1 Establishing the objectives of ideological and political education in the course of digital image processing

According to the problems reflected in the analysis of academic situation, teachers should combine the knowledge architecture of digital image processing and teaching practice to determine the educational goals of implementing ideological and political education in the course. It is expected that through the knowledge learning and ability cultivation of this course, students' quality can be improved in the following aspects.

1) Enhance the sense of mission and responsibility, maintain a positive attitude towards life

In recent years, information technology represented by artificial intelligence and Big data has developed rapidly, and many applications closely related to image processing have changed the production and life style of society. The realization of the Chinese Dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation cannot be achieved without the joint efforts of the entire nation. The great struggle to achieve the great dream should strengthen students' sense of patriotism and national pride, stimulate their motivation to work hard and make them full of confidence in the development of the country, society, and individuals.

2) Advocate the spirit of science, cultivate scientific thinking and attitude

The spirit of science is the most precious spiritual wealth in human civilization, originating from the spirit of seeking knowledge. With the continuous development of scientific practice, its connotation is constantly enriched. Understand the characteristics of interdisciplinary integration, inspire innovative ideas and awareness, and cultivate a scientific attitude to integrating theory with practice, scientific rigor, and seeking truth from facts. The development of digital image processing technology cannot be separated from continuous technological innovation and practical exploration. Many image processing methods embody universal scientific thinking, learning image processing knowledge and its applications is also a process of cultivating scientific thinking methods.

3) Strengthen awareness of rules, cultivate the sense of collaboration and craftsmanship

The study of image processing emphasizes the implementation of various processing algorithms through programming, and correct results can be obtained by strictly following the algorithm principles and programming standards. Comparing with it, following the rules is the premise of maintaining a good social order. We should abide by public policy doctrine and treat people honestly and friendly. Through teaching practice activities in

groups, the teamwork ability of student is honed, and continuous improvement of image processing algorithms and processing effects are achieved in a good atmosphere of learning and catching up, cultivating the spirit of craftsmanship.

4.2 Integrate ideological and political elements into course knowledge points

Combined with the specific knowledge of digital image processing, to carry on the teaching design to the digital image processing and excavate the ideological and political elements, through diversified teaching activities to strengthen the value identification of Chinese traditional excellent culture and to cultivate the feelings of home and country, road confidence, theory confidence, system confidence and culture confidence. The ideological and political elements which can be incorporated into the chapters of the digital image processing course designed by the teachers in Table 1.

Table 1: Combination of knowledge points in digital image processing and ideological and political elements

Knowledge points	Teaching content	Ideological and political "integration elements"
Introduction	The development history of digital image processing, as well as some new scientific research achievements and successful cases,	Enhance students' national pride and confidence, shape their correct outlook on life, and contribute to the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.
Basic knowledge of digital image processing	For color model analysis, Chinese knotting images and ceramic images can be used	Promote traditional culture and strengthen the belief of cultural self-confidence and civilization self-confidence.
Image transformation	Parallel transformation in image Geometric transformation, analyze the application of translation parallel transformation in textile industry and hairdressing industry	Students' social responsibility.
Image enhancement	Sharpening and smoothing, Different smoothing and sharpening methods; frequency domain image processing	Specific analysis of specific problems through philosophical thinking; The patriotism of students and the spirit of a great craftsman.
Image restoration	Introduction applications of image restoration technology such as Chang'e's exploration of the moon, has expanded to include the application of students' patriotism and mission,	A sense of home and mission, social responsibility and craftsmanship
Image compression coding	Introducing digital watermarking technology, effectively ensure intellectual property rights and educate legal cconcepts in data transmission	Legal concept
Image segmentation	Engineering application cases ,the design of recycling garbage classifiers	Effectively recycling and utilization of energy, hands-on ability and scientific and technological innovation awareness, and cultivate a sense of social responsibility and mission.
Image describes	The pixel connectivity, and the eight connection, four connection	Philosophical thinking of on contradiction theory.

V. Analysis and Reflection on the Teaching Effect of Ideological and Political Education

The integration of ideological and political elements into digital image processing, as well as the addition of course case has improved students' participation in the curriculum. In the past three years, the integration of ideological and political cases into professional knowledge and theory has enlivened the class, has significantly increased students' enthusiasm for answering questions. Students majoring in electronic information engineering have not only gained knowledge and improved their abilities, but also developed a scientific and technological confidence, social responsibility, and a pragmatic and innovative attitude. More students are very enthusiastic about the research work of image processing technology. They have participated in the National Engineering Training Competition, Smart Car, Internet plus, Electronic Design Competition, Undergraduate Innovation Competition, Blue Bridge Cup Competition and other events, have won 11 national awards, 49 provincial awards and issued 18 papers; The satisfaction rate of the comprehensive evaluation of the teaching teachers reached 100%.

During the process of ideological and political construction, the course team teachers reorganized the teaching syllabus and explored the ideological and political elements of knowledge points, which not only improved their professional theoretical level, but also greatly improved their personal ideological and political cultivation and philosophical literacy. As an important guide on the path of students' growth, teachers should continuously improve their professional standards and also improve their ideological and political qualities, setting a good example for students. Therefore, teachers should consciously strengthen the guidance of ideological and political work on their subjects and majors, should understand society, national conditions, international politics, the development trends of world science and technology, should strengthen their own ideological and moral level and integrate professional knowledge and ideological and political elements through continuous learning and thinking, carry out ideological and political education in teaching and actively participate in the construction of teaching demonstration courses, cultivating innovative talents with strong ideological and political skills, solid professional skills and a combination of morality and talent for new engineering.

VI. Conclusion

Curriculum ideological and political education is an important component of higher education in universities. Guided by the teaching philosophy of "value shaping, ability cultivation, and knowledge impartation", combining with the characteristics of digital image processing professional, ideological and political education in courses is cleverly integrated. The analysis mainly focuses on the strategies of integrating ideological and political education into professional courses, the integration of ideological and political elements in course knowledge, and the teaching effectiveness of ideological and political education in courses. The construction of the ideological and political system in the curriculum is still in the initial exploration stage, and how to deeply integrate ideological and political elements into professional curriculum teaching still needs to be further deepened, continuously improved, and continuously promoted, so as to achieve a silent educational effect and the fundamental task of moral education.

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